

Discovering data with the ESCAPE Science Analysis Platform

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Abstract.

The ESCAPE Science Analysis Platform (ESAP) will become a richly featured platform and online service gateway which gives users the ability to discover, access and combine data from multiple collections, before staging them for subsequent processing and analysis. We present the results of ongoing work during 2020, which has produced a Prototype Gateway Interface (PGI) that integrates data discovery functionality and supports numerous data formats from heterogeneous archives and data sources representing several scientific disciplines.

1. ESCAPE and the ESCAPE Science Analysis Platform

ESCAPE (European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle physics ESFRI research infrastructures) brings together the astronomy, astroparticle and particle physics communities to build the astronomy and particle physics cell of the European Open Science Cloud.

ESCAPE aims to enhance the potential for scientific discovery by creating a cross-border and multi-disciplinary open environment, according to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles. ESCAPE recognises that modern large-scale scientific facilities face many common challenges and share many common capabilities. By building infrastructures that streamline collaboration between different facilities, ESCAPE strives to avoid needless duplication of effort and to encourage the development of joint multiwavelength and multi-messenger capabilities in astronomy, astrophysics and particle astrophysics communities.

At the heart of the ESCAPE initiative is the ESFRI Science Analysis Platform (ESAP). ESAP will become a online service gateway with the capability to access and combine data from multiple collections and stage them for subsequent processing and analysis. It will provide a flexible science platform for the analysis of open access data. Users will be able to select data and process them using a wide-range of software tools and packages developed by and in support of the facilities that participate in ESCAPE. Users will also be able to define and execute their own custom workflows, and take advantage of the underlying high performance computing infrastructure.

In this proceeding we present a prototype suite of online data discovery tools that have been developed for the ESAP. The *Prototype Gateway Interface* (PGI) is built using industry-standard software frameworks and is designed to be flexible and extensible

with a modular structure that encapsulates its different functional components. The PGI implements a server-side back-end written in Python using the *Django* framework¹. It uses the *Django REST Framework*² to communicate with a browser-based JavaScript front-end, built using the *React* framework³.

From a service-user perspective, the PGI design provides a unified data-discovery interface that enables data from a wide range of diverse services and scientific disciplines to be searched for and marked for subsequent retrieval by the data analysis components of ESAP that are being developed in parallel.

For data providers, the PGI is designed to enable straightforward integration using a modular plug-in structure. The PGI aims to be agnostic about the details of remote data sources. As outlined in §2, integration may require no coding at all, and in the more complex situations (see e.g. §4), only a small handful of Python and JavaScript methods need to be implemented.

To let users mark data they discover, the PGI implements a simple user profile model that includes a unique identifier and a set of items that the user has marked. The marked items are encoded as JSON objects to avoid over-prescribing how data entities should be described and identified for retrieval. User profiles are stored by the PGI back end in a light-weight SQLite database⁴, and can be retrieved using a RESTful API or using a lightweight Python client.

In subsequent sections we introduce more features of the PGI, using as examples some of the data source that have already been successfully integrated.

2. ESAP for Astronomers

The umbrella terms astronomy and astrophysics encompass a dizzying pan-global diversity of telescopes, instruments and related disciplines. Astrophysical processes manifest phenomena that can be characterised using observations that span the spectrum of electromagnetic radiation. Modern astronomy also relies on other astrophysical messengers, including charged cosmic rays, neutrinos and even gravitational waves. Moreover, forthcoming astrophysical facilities like the *Rubin Observatory* (Ivezić et al. 2019), the *Cherenkov Telescope Array* (CTA Mazin 2019), and the *Square Kilometre Array*⁵ (SKA) will deliver exquisite astrophysical data in unprecedented volumes - astronomy is entering the era of Big Data . The challenge of designing a framework to unify this panoply of heterogeneous data sources, with associated differences in data formats, ontologies and scales is formidable. Fortunately however, this challenge is already being addressed using a set of internationally recognised standards defined by the International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA⁶). One of the core components of the PGI is a generic interface that enables discovery of Virtual Observatory (VO)

¹<https://www.djangoproject.com>

²<https://www.django-rest-framework.org>

³<https://reactjs.org>

⁴<https://www.sqlite.org/index.html>

⁵<https://www.skatelescope.org>

⁶<http://ivoa.net/>

resources that comply with the IVOA standards. The PGI interfaces seamlessly with Virtual Observatory (VO) registries that implement the *RegTAP* protocol (Arviset et al. 2017; Osuna et al. 2008). This enables discovery of VO compliant services using any combination of keyword, waveband and VO Service type (e.g. TAP, cone search etc.). PGI users may then query any of the registries that meet their requirements discover by issuing ADQL (Demleitner 2015) queries from the PGI web interface. Future PGI developments will include ADQL query validation and ultimately a graphical query interface for simple queries. The interface displays the query results and allows users to select data items they need and save their selection for later processing or analysis.

As well as supporting astrophysical data source that support VO protocols, the PGI also integrates bespoke support for specific astronomy catalogues, like those from the The Westerbork Synthesis Radio Telescope (WSRT) APERTIF datasets (e.g. Adams et al. 2020).

3. ESAP for Particle and Nuclear Physicists

The particle and nuclear physics communities are renowned for building instruments that generate vast quantities of experimental data, which in turn require substantial high throughput and high performance computing facilities to process. Since the computing facilities that analyse the data are not typically co-located with the experimental facilities that produce them, particle and nuclear physics data are typically stored in a distributed manner and replicated to the local storage of different compute facilities as required. To provide straightforward discovery of distributed Big Data sets produces and used by the particle and nuclear physics communities, the PGI implements an interface with the *Rucio* data management framework (Barisits et al. 2019). The PGI implementation interfaces with *Rucio* via its RESTful API and automatically discovers a list of *Rucio* scopes to which the user has access. Users may then search for Data Identifiers (DIDs), files and replicas that are stored within the ESCAPE Data Lake, which they can then mark for further processing. The *Rucio* REST API provides extensive functionality, and only a small subset of this has been integrated into the PGI so far. However, the PGI integration has been designed so that new *Rucio* REST API endpoints can be added with a single line of Python code, so future extensions will be very straightforward to implement.

4. ESAP for Citizen Science

Modern scientific experiments produce diverse, complex data in unprecedented volumes. In addition to substantial computational resources, extracting maximum scientific insight from these data requires novel and increasingly sophisticated data analysis techniques. Even today, in the era of Deep Learning, some scientific analyses remain particularly challenging to automate, and the scales of modern datasets prohibit manual analysis by a single scientist or even a whole scientific team or consortium. Citizen science (CS) is research tool which can help to address these analysis challenges. By recruiting non-expert volunteers from around the World and reducing analyses to simple pattern-matching tasks that require little or no professional training large scale datasets can be efficiently analysed. A particularly promising use for CS is as a way to generate

accurate labels for observed (i.e. not simulated) data that can be used to train Deep Learning models.

ESCAPE promotes CS and has already supported two successful projects, engaging over 15000 citizen volunteers⁷⁸. The completed ESAP will facilitate creation of new citizen science projects using data that are accessed via the platform. The PGI allows users to discover and explore CS data collected using the Zooniverse web platform⁹. Zooniverse projects are composed of several semantically distinct entities. *Projects* are subdivided into *workflows*, within which citizen scientists interact with *subjects* drawn from *subject sets* to perform *analysis tasks* and thereby provide *classifications* of the subjects. Zooniverse data reflect this complex entity relationship. They are diverse with a custom data format and metadata that (unlike VO resources) do not conform with an internationally agreed standard. The PGI simplifies the complex Zooniverse data model for its users by automatically discovering available metadata fields for different entities and allowing users to retrieve values for specific subsets of metadata that are of interest. Users may then mark specific subsets of CS data that meet specific selection criteria so that they can be retrieved and analysed later.

5. Ongoing Work

Work to improve the PGI continues and in the coming months we aim to integrate full support for user authentication and authorization (AAI) by interfacing directly with ESCAPE's Identity and Access Management (IAM) system.

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⁷<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/hughdickinson/galaxy-zoo-clump-scout>

⁸<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/chrismrp/radio-galaxy-zoo-lofar>

⁹<https://www.zooniverse.org>